

Table 1. Maintainers to Chinese cytoplasmic-genetic male-sterile lines, New Delhi.

Test cross	Pollen sterility (%)
Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/ CRM13-32-111	83.3
Er-Jiu-Nan 1A/ Pusa 169-33-1-1	98.3
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/Bhavani	100.0
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/BPI 76-1	100.0
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/CO 42	100.0
V20A/Basmati mutant	100.0
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/ADT33	83.3

restorers, they have not been evaluated for agronomic value in terms of exploitable hybrid vigor. They are, however,

promising because they have stable yield performance, good maturity, and good cooking quality. □

Table 2. Restorer lines for Chinese cytoplasmic-genetic male-sterile lines, New Delhi.

Test cross	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet fertility (%)
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/IR30	4.8	93
Zhen Shan 97A/Pusa 167-120-3-2	8.5	92
Er-Jiu Nan 1A/Pusa 150-21-1-1	5.0	93.5

Evaluation of some cytoplasmic male sterile (cms), maintainer, and restorer lines in Bangladesh

H. C. Sarkar, plant breeder; and N. M. Miah, principal plant breeder, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

Thirty-two rice varieties or lines including a set of 5 cms and 5 maintainer lines, and a set of 9 maintainer and 13 restorer lines

supplied by IRRI were evaluated for stability, adaptability, and agronomic suitability under Bangladesh agroclimatic conditions. The tests were held at the BRRI-Joydebpur station in 1982 aman (Jul-Dec).

Each entry was transplanted in a 2.5-m single row at 25- × 25-cm spacing with one 30-day-old seedling per hill in a randomized complete block design with 2 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 60-25-15 kg NPK/ha. Agronomic and flowering traits were recorded and reaction to

bacterial leaf blight and sheath rot was noted.

Only one cms line, Pankhari 203A, and its maintainer Pankhari 203B performed better under local conditions. However, pollen sterility in the cms lines was incomplete. Two other maintainers — IR19657-87-3-3 and IET3257 — and six restorer lines also showed good adaptability (see table). Performance of cms lines V20A, Wu 10A, and Ms 577A was poor although they had good stability (95-100% pollen sterility). □

Cms, maintainer, and restorer lines that performed well in Bangladesh.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 1st flowering	Days to complete flowering	Panicles (no./plant)	Flag leaf length (cm)	Disease		Phenotypic acceptability		Pollen fertility (%)
						BLB	ShR	Vegetative stage	Maturity	
Pankhari 203A	115	17	88	21	27.3	5	5	3	5	15-25
Pankhari 203B	128	83	91	14	29.4	5	5	3	5	80-90
IR19657-87-3-3	97	93	111	13	31.5	1	2	4	4	85-95
IET3257	92	94	106	9	28.1	1	2	4	6	80-90
IR26	84	102	119	24	31.4	1	1	5	5	85-90
IR42	90	101	118	15	27.9	2	1	4	5	80-85
IR46	106	94	111	17	26.4	1	1	4	2	75-80
IR52	96	86	104	16	32.6	1	1	5	5	80-90
IR54	98	93	107	17	28.4	1	1	4	3	80-90
IR2307-247-2-2-3	83	88	107	17	31.3	1	1	5	5	80-85

Extent of natural outcrossing of V20A, a cytoplasmic male-sterile (cms) line, in Bangladesh

H. C. Sarkar, plant breeder; and N. M. Miah, principal plant breeder, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dhaka, Bangladesh

BRRI initiated collaborative research on hybrid rice with IRRI in 1982. Successful hybrid rice production depends on

large amounts of outcrossing of cms lines. We studied field production of hybrid seed using cms line V20A and its maintainer, V20B (pollen source).

Twenty-five 25-day-old V20B seedlings were transplanted 1 seedling/hill in 5 rows at 20- × 20-cm spacing in an isolated plot. At the same time 30-day-old V20A seedlings were planted around V20B seedlings at various distances — 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 cm — to maintain the same spacing and seedlings/hill as in

V20B. Only one panicle of each V20A plant was bagged before anthesis. The

Percent seed set on V20A at various distances from the pollen source V20B, BRRI, 1982.

Distance (cm) from V20B	Seed set (%) on V20A
20	2.51
40	1.45
60	0.93
80	0.79
100	0.59